

Improving Writing Abilities by Using GLIL in Teaching Geography

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ABSTRACT

Research work answers the questions like what is the effectiveness of the CLIL method in the development of speaking and writing skills of students in geography lessons? The main problem in the study is the emergence of difficulties in understanding the content of the subject in students studying geography in a second language. The reason is the uncertainty of the content of geography in the Kazakh language by the students of the Russian class, as a result of which the idea cannot be written in the Kazakh language during the performance of the forming and summary assessment tasks. The relevance of the study lies in the application in practice of integrated subject and language learning in modern samples of lessons. Integrated learning subject matter and language /GLIL/ learning the subjects through a second/third languages. The study provided for the simultaneous implementation of subject and language objectives for educational purposes. The study used methods of questioning, interview, communication, communication with a psychologist, curator, parents, teachers of the Kazakh language. During the lesson, various approaches of the GLIL method aimed at the formation of subject knowledge were studied, as well as the positive and negative sides were evaluated. The study provides examples of writing by GordanStorbort, Alan Crawford, and studied the second language and studied the subject area, the mastery of language is the main achievement of the student in the integration of the subject and language, as well as a method aimed at the study of the subject and the study of language through the subject. Jim Cummins in 2004, as a result of his study by immigrants in Canada, determined that it takes two or three years to learn a second/third language to acquire basic interpersonal communication skills, and it takes five years for cognitive academic skills, and we are confident that the results of the research will be clear in the coming years.

Keywords: *Method GLIL, Pronunciation Skills, Writing Skills, Scaffolding*

Introduction

Integrated subject and language training / GLIL / - mastery of subjects of the second / third languages and mastery of this subject area perfectly mastery of the language, that is, subject and language goals are simultaneously implemented. The results of international studies show that

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students who master subjects through the second / third languages have high motivation, skillful, creative and knowledge in their native language, higher than students who studied in their native language, while relying on international experience, teaching subjects in a second language does not adversely affect the achievement and development of students' skills, but, on the contrary, will allow you to master the languages at the academic level, make extensive use of additional sources of information, understand it is supposed comprehensive study of the geography and the formation patriotic feelings. Therefore, we attach great importance to teaching geography in the Kazakh language, but in our practice we encountered some difficulties in teaching geography in Russian classes, that is, not understanding the content, although the students have an interest in the subject, as a result of which the interest in the subject has become outdated, some students do not can understand the content, do not know how to use words correctly, do not make up the sentence structure, do not repeat homework, do not have time and do not have time, respectively, a large number of additional classes, and on the part of the parents, “why do I need to study the subject in Kazakh?”, “change the program”, “children do not understand.”

Based on these observations, this academic year we started the process of researching activities with the aim of improving the educational process and training, establishing the formation of language skills of students in Russian classes, which became the impetus for our experience. In this regard, as was said above, the students of the Russian class are unclear of the content of geography in the Kazakh language, as a result of which, when completing tasks in formative and consolidated assessment, the game cannot be written in the Kazakh language, respectively, led to a decrease in the quality of education, getting low scores in the internal aggregate grades of the good. A similar focus group included 7 - Russian classes, stages of research, which covered the period from September 2017 to April 2018. “How does the GLIL method contribute to the development of writing skills of students in teaching geography in a second language?” The study was conducted through questionnaires, interviews with a psychologist, curator, parents, and teachers of the Kazakh language. In connection with the study of the subject of geography in the Kazakh language, the main relevance of our study was the integrated teaching of the subject and language, including the formation of language skills among students. Various data related to the study were collected and processed, which form and SIA work, photographs, survey results, interviews, diary, lesson progress, analysis of the learning process.

For this, students, curators, parents helped us, and only private geography teachers have no shortcomings, because to discuss it, we had to consult with other subject teachers, a “critical friend”. As a “critical friend”, we listened to the opinions of colleagues at the Kazakh language department.

In the future, the only problem that we want to change is the consideration of effective methods in the process of teaching in the classroom, so that students perfectly master the geography in a second language. Is the methodology of the teacher and student organized for the implementation of the principles of teaching and are the didactic goals taken into account in the choice of teaching methods, features of the subject, age characteristics, individual abilities?

Currently, there is a very large flow of scientific information, it is known that training time is limited. One of the most important requirements is the identification of methods and effective learning content, so our goal is integrated learning of the subject and language, we chose to organize them using the GLIL-integrated learning method. There are several definitions of the method of integrated learning of a subject and language, for example, “a method that considers language as a means of preparing for intercultural understanding, creating an international approach and improving the quality of general education” or “a method aimed at studying a subject and learning a language through a subject”, as well as “improving the study of the language in the study of subjects through the second or third language and the study of subject areas, that is, the parallel achievement of subject and language goals. "Based on this, The integrated teaching of subject and language acquired a new definition in the context of Nazarbayev Intellectual Schools, which is reflected in the top three for educational policy: “the formation of a citizen of Kazakhstan who speaks three languages, speaks three languages, speaks three languages, is able to conduct dialogue on various topics that assess culture of one’s people and who understands and respects the culture of other peoples”, therefore, when studying a subject in a second language, when integrating the subject and the language, language ki.

In the lesson of integrated teaching of the subject and language, although most of the time is given to work with text, it is necessary, if possible, to cover all types of language skills. When choosing educational material, it is necessary to select texts that correspond to the age characteristics and levels of language training of students. Students take quickly if the texts are divided into small parts, accompanied by drawings, diagrams, maps. When planning a lesson, a teacher can transmit part of the material in the form of audio text, and using the methods of study learning, you can master the material through dialogue and interviews. When preparing educational tasks, it is necessary to provide for differentiation taking into account the language level of students in the subject. During the lesson, clearly disclose the objectives and expected results of the lesson; create a favorable educational environment for learning languages; develop four language skills (reading, listening, writing, pronunciation); if necessary, repeat vague sentences and phrases to students repeatedly.; use light vocabulary to perceive students; work with support words. An important stage of activity is the collection of data, therefore, focus classes were first selected, data was collected using quantitative and qualitative methods, based on triangulation.

In order for the first study to be reliable, we used the triangulation method, that is, we used qualitative methods with the quantitative method, the top three schools talked with parents, teachers, students, although not all.

In an interview with individual students, we give examples of questions: student number 1 "studying geography in the Kazakh language was very difficult for me at first, since I do not understand the Kazakh language, for example, voluminous texts, the term words, I find it difficult to understand in the future the study of geography in the Kazakh language is very important, so it would be better if the lesson was group work and translation into Russian".

Student No. 2 “reading geography in the Kazakh language did not work out for me, because I used the dictionary and understood Kazakh well, but it was difficult, I couldn’t make sentences and write it, read the text, don’t do it, don’t do it, don’t do it, don’t do it , not to be in time, not to be in time, not to be in time in pair, or in group reading, it is necessary to study geography in the Kazakh language, because we studied the Kazakh language only in the lesson, we used various methods, they play well in the game form. ”

The answer received during the conversation with the curator: “students are interested in the subject, but in the internal total grades, students get low scores, for which it is necessary to allocate time for more writing and speech in the lesson and to do work in a pair of a child who knows and does not speak Kazakh language. ”

The answer received during an interview with parents: “studying geography in the Kazakh language is very difficult, I can’t help him at home because I don’t understand the Kazakh language, so I got a tutor, I got Kazakh books, but their benefits are small, children are constantly they speak Russian, he loves geography, but not understanding, I’m afraid that he will lose content, on the one hand, he supported that in the future Kazakh is in fear that it does not know the content of the subject ”

In order to find out the individual abilities of the classes, we met with a psychologist, in the conversation we determined the individual abilities of the students, and we noticed that no one from the general class chose the subject of geography, and according to the abilities of the three students separately, the type of thinking according to Gardner of student No. 1, has leadership abilities, is close to sports, shows interest in football, tennis, boxing, mathematics, physics, chemistry. The type of thinking of students according to Gardner is a logical and internal personal intellect, loves to draw, play the electric guitar, shows interest in the subject of physics. Student No. 3 thinks according to Gardner sports intelligence, there is no interest in the subject.

Armed with the necessary information, we started working with students, set the goal and objectives of training, as we teach our students. The study of students was carried out in each lesson, at the initial stage, the forming assessments of the achievement of educational goals were at the level: No. 1, the student has high motivation in the lesson, and the student has good writing skills, that is, we were looking for answers to questions about what results we expect from the next lesson. Pupils of school No. 2 wrote at their level, but the structure of the sentence is not correct, because the game, which I will say on paper, encounters difficulties, they know what to write in general. Pupil No. 3 did not write at all, because he did not write, did not use dictionaries, we all know this.

For students of 7th grades, depending on age, methods and techniques were chosen. Using these methods, we developed a lesson plan, intended to give students freedom in the lesson, and learned how to wait a long time for answers to questions, because the Russian student being considered was mentioned in the game, which we say in a short time. 1, 2, 3 students do not show interest in classes, but perform tasks as they become available.

First of all, we used the GLIL method called “Dictogloss”, since to eliminate some obstacles in the development of the subject it is necessary to support through language support

(scaffolding), for example, students work with couples on the topic “water resources”, in one of which the text is completely given, in one of which multipoint places are given, the goal is one to be read, the second to listen, put words instead of empty dots, and then check together. The second approach is a visual approach, working with video materials through which language skills are formed, that is, showing a video on a topic. We prepare and put questions into the class before the screen to answer these questions, listen to the video, answer existing questions, then write small stories or essays using these sentences, that is, they completely guessed the writing skills. As we noticed, while listening to three students in the study, student number 1 was able to record the hearing, as he found answers to questions. If student number 2 does not fully verbally answer questions, then the game was very good, and student number 3 fully answered questions, and he found it a little difficult with his word, because the vocabulary is even smaller.

But the drawback of this method is that when listening to the video, the students did not understand the word, therefore, when writing an essay, they didn't answer the question correctly, the students' interest in the subject woke up, they began to look at the lesson differently, another noticed that the students who received the study, began to use the words correctly when writing an essay, but in determining the topic of each lesson, we had a video film, which was a very good method for us, as it was possible to express our opinions without fail.

The second of the visual techniques used during the lesson is the method of "info communication interval" (gap), through which communication between students is carried out. When studying the topic “world nations” we used the “pictures speak” method, 3 people work in groups. In group 1, the student receives a photograph, in the group he verbally talks about what he saw in this picture, 2 students in the group write what they heard, and 3 students draw what they heard. As a result, 1 student develops pronunciation skills by correctly expressing their thoughts, 2 - the student's ability to draw with listening skills increases, and 3 students develop subscription skills with listening. This was one of the most convenient for us, methods are, firstly, active all the students are working, secondly, the student holding the picture increases the vocabulary for the correct event in the picture, while the others carefully listen to his statements on the right paper and create the conditions for interaction. There were natural phenomena, thematic maps, photographs about population density.

In the course of research in the activity, we very deeply studied our pedagogical personality, and most importantly, it was very interesting for us to observe the changes taking place in the school. Each of them has its own individual characteristics, taking into account which we tried to create conditions for success in increasing interest in learning.

The organization of instruction and training through GLIL, thereby, integrated language and subject teaching, had a positive effect on the development of relationships between students and the development of a subject in a second language. In each lesson, we went to the right choice of methods to attract students to reading. During the study, you can see the growth dynamics with both all classes and students individually controlled, by the formation of subscription skills. You can see an increase in their interest in the subject, the development of language skills, including writing skills, activity and assignments in the lesson, and participation in reflection.

What is the effectiveness of glil?

The effectiveness of glil sought, first of all, to integrate the subject and language in an integrated manner, to teach students to read, that is, to focus on self-mastery of the language, to teach students to communicate with each other, to help each other, not a single student was left in stone, that is, inclusive learning. During the lesson, 5 effective methods were used: dictogloss, watching a video, “pictures say working with thermal words,” hot stool ”/ as a result:

* able to provide active learning through various learning strategies that promote the development of student abilities .;

• for the use of new forms of language learning or specific subject terminology can provide students with many speech and written opportunities;

* able to stimulate relations between students;

* able to improve commutatvit, supporting speech:

To summarize:

* First of all, when communicating with students studying in a second language, the teacher must speak with a short, clear and simple speed;

* the use of differentiation is required due to the fact that during the lesson there are students with a mixed language level .;

* The teacher should evaluate, constantly encourage and support the small achievements of students. Only then do students wake up to learn the language .;

• during individual work with students, it is necessary to pay attention to the necessary lexical minimum, that is, give the necessary words, phrases, ready-made phrases (simple sentences) that can use any word when inserting into colloquial speech.

It should be borne in mind that grammatical topics, complex concepts should not be given. This prevents the child from talking, causes fear that grammatically I cannot speak correctly.

Jim Cummins in 2004, as a result of his study by immigrants in Canada, determined that in studying a second / third language, a basic person needs two or three years to acquire intercultural skills, and for cognitive academic skills it takes five years, since we work with these classes 2 years, this study does not stop there, this is a continuation, we still see in practice other ways of this method. The secret to the success of the teaching profession is continuing education and continuous growth, and therefore, these studies will help our professional growth and continuing education, so we are confident that this will be a continuation of the study.

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